

Supplementary information

Evolutionary history of alpha satellite DNA in Cercopithecini: comparative cytogenomics highlights the diversification pattern of primate centromere repeats

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Figure S1 - FISH analysis of the C3 and C4 alpha satellite families in species from the terrestrial clade. Metaphase chromosomes are shown in blue (DAPI counterstain). (A) Hybridization signal of probe C4a (green) on *A. lhoesti* chromosomes. (B) Hybridization signal of probe C3b (red) on *A. lhoesti* chromosomes. (C) Hybridization signal of probe C4a (green) on *E. patas* chromosomes. Arrows point to weakly hybridized pericentromeres. The star-shaped arrow indicates a labeled interstitial locus on a chromosome long arm. Scale bar = 10 μm .

Figure S2 - FISH analysis of the C5 alpha satellite family in species from the terrestrial clade. Metaphase chromosomes are shown in blue (DAPI counterstain). All images show hybridization with probe C5a (green) and represent original, unprocessed data. (A) *A. lhoesti* chromosomes following a standard post-hybridization wash at 63 °C. (B) *A. lhoesti* chromosomes following a stringent post-hybridization wash at 68 °C. (C) *E. patas* chromosomes following a standard post-hybridization wash at 63 °C. (D) *E. patas* chromosomes following a stringent post-hybridization wash at 68 °C. Scale bar = 10 μ m.

Figure S3 - Classification of alpha satellite monomers, retrieved from *Cercopithecus pogonias* dimeric sequences, within the C3 and C4 families.

Previous analyses of *C. pogonias* alpha satellite monomers (Cacheux et al., 2018) identified the C1, C2, C5, and C6 (sub)families within that dataset. This figure utilizes a separate set of dimeric sequences to characterize the C3 and C4 families. Raw data for these dimeric sequences were deposited in the NIH Short Read Archive (SRA accession number: SRX1959817).

Following the methodology presented by Cacheux et al. (2016, 2018), 2,360 dimeric alpha satellite sequences were retrieved from *C. pogonias* genomic DNA via XmnI enzymatic digestion, gel electrophoresis fractionation, and Ion Torrent NGS. A subset of 2,295 dimers, specifically those lacking the XmnI site between their constitutive left and right monomers, were selected for the subsequent analysis and split *in silico* into left and right monomers.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) projections are shown for (A) left monomers and (B) right monomers, based on the normalized frequency vectors of 5-mers (pentanucleotides). Each sequence is represented by a point, colored according to its assignment (determined by hierarchical classification) to the alpha satellite families: C2 (pastel green), C3 (dark pink), or C4 (light pink). (C) presents a phylogenetic tree (Neighbor-Joining method, K2P model), constructed from a random subsample of 250 left monomers and 250 right monomers. Alignment for this phylogenetic analysis was performed using MUSCLE (Edgar, 2004). The color code in the tree matches the family assignments described for (A) and (B).

Figure S4 - Inter-species comparison of alpha satellite monomers retrieved from *Cercopithecus pogonias* and *Allochrocebus solatus* dimeric sequences

Following the methodology presented by Cacheux et al. (2016, 2018), this analysis compares the left and right monomers from *C. pogonias* dimeric alpha satellites with the C2, C3, and C4 monomers previously identified within *A. solatus* dimeric alpha satellites (Cacheux et al., 2016). The dimeric sequences were retrieved from *C. pogonias* genomic DNA via XmnI enzymatic digestion, gel electrophoresis fractionation, and Ion Torrent NGS (as described in the Fig. S3 legend). Only dimeric sequences that did not display the XmnI site between their constitutive left and right monomers were considered for this analysis.

(A) and (B) show PCA projections based on the normalized 5-mer frequency vectors (using principal components 1 and 2). The PCA space was determined solely by the *C. pogonias* left monomers (A) or right monomers (B), and *A. solatus* sequences were mapped onto this reference space for visualization. (A) illustrates the localization of the *C. solatus* C2 (pastel green) and C3 (dark pink) left monomers. (B) illustrates the localization of the *C. solatus* C2 (pastel green) and C4 (light pink) right monomers. Each point in (A) and (B) represents one sequence.

(C) presents a phylogenetic tree (Neighbor-Joining method, K2P model) constructed from a random subsample of sequences. The tree includes monomers from eight distinct groups, with 50 sequences randomly selected from each, for a total of 400 sequences. These groups are composed of *C. pogonias* C2 left, C2 right, C3 left, and C4 right monomers, and *C. solatus* C2 left, C2 right, C3 left, and C4 right monomers. The *A. solatus* sequences are specifically indicated by arrows. Alignment for the phylogenetic analysis was performed using MUSCLE. The color code in the tree is consistent with the family assignments described for (A) and (B).

Figure S5 - FISH analysis of the C4 alpha satellite family on *Cercopithecus pogonias* chromosomes. The C4a' probe (red) is hybridized to *C. pogonias* chromosomes (blue, DAPI counterstain). White arrows point to faint pericentromeric C4a' signals. The red arrow marks the Y chromosome, which shows no C4a' hybridization. This result contrasts with the strong Y-linked signal previously reported in *A. solatus* (Cacheux et al., 2016). Scale bar = 10 μ m.

Figure S6 - FISH analysis of the C1 alpha satellite family on *Allenopithecus nigroviridis* chromosomes. Metaphase chromosomes are shown in blue (DAPI counterstain). Probes C1a (red) and C1b (green) were hybridized simultaneously, with the C2b probe included as a sequence competitor for the C1b hybridization. (A) Hybridization signal of probe C1a (red). (B) Hybridization signal of probe C1b (green). (C) Merged image of (A) and (B) demonstrating the non-overlapping localization of the C1a and C1b probes. Scale bar = 10 μm .

Figure S7 - FISH analysis of the C2 alpha satellite family on *Macaca sylvanus* chromosomes. Metaphase chromosomes are shown in blue (DAPI counterstain). (A) Hybridization signal of probe C2a (green). (B) Hybridization signal of probe C2b (red). (C) Merged image of (A) and (B) demonstrating the non-overlapping localization of the two probes on the *M. sylvanus* chromosomes. (D) Magnified view of image (C). Scale bar = 10 μm .

Figure S8 - FISH analysis of the C3 and C4 alpha satellite families on *Macaca sylvanus* chromosomes. Chromosomes are colored in blue (DAPI counterstain). (A) Hybridization signal of probe C3b (red). (B) Hybridization signal of probe C4a (green). (C) Merged image of (A) and (B) demonstrating the non-overlapping localization of the C3 and C4 probes. (D) Magnified view of image (C). Scale bar = 10 μ m.

(Figure S9A, 1/4)

(Figure S9B, 2/4)

(Figure S9C, 3/4)

(Figure S9D, 4/4)

Figure S9 - Distribution pattern of the C2 alpha satellite family on Cercopithecini chromosomes. Hybridization signal of probe C2b (green) on metaphase chromosomes (red, propidium iodide counterstain) of: (A) *A. nigroviridis*, (B) *E. patas*, (C) *C. roloway*, and (D) *C. cephus*. Chromosomes are arranged according to reference karyotypes (Dutrillaux et al., 1978, 1980, 1982, 1988; Moulin et al. 2008).

(Figure S10A, 1/3)

(Figure S10B, 2/3)

(Figure S10C, 3/3)

Figure S10 - Distribution pattern of the C5 alpha satellite family on Cercopithecini chromosomes. Hybridization signal of probe C5a (green) on metaphase chromosomes (red, propidium iodide counterstain) of (A) *E. patas* (labels observed on pairs 2, 8, 20 and 21-26), (B) *C. roloway* (labels observed on pairs 9, 10, 17, 18, 21, and 26) and (C) *C. cephus* (labels observed on pairs 5, 8, 9, 18, 22, and X chromosome). Chromosome arrangements are based on the references detailed in the Figure S9 legend.

Figure S11 - Distribution pattern of the C6 alpha satellite family on *Cercopithecus cephus* chromosomes. Hybridization signal of probe C6a (green) on *C. cephus* metaphase chromosomes (red, propidium iodide counterstain) (labels observed on pairs 9, 18, 19 and 24-32). Chromosome arrangements are based on the references detailed in the Figure S9 legend.

(Figure S12, 1/7)

(Figure S12, 2/7)

(Figure S12, 3/7)

(Figure S12, 4/7)

(Figure S12, 5/7)

(Figure S12, 6/7)

(Figure S12, 7/7)

Figure S12 - Alignment of homologous chromosomes based on R-banding patterns across Cercopithecini species. The presumed ancestral chromosomes of Cercopithecidae (shown on the left) are aligned with their homologs in *A. nigroviridis* (ANI), *E. patas* (EPA), *A. solatus* (ASO), *C. roloway* (CRO), *C. cephus* (CCE), and *C. pogonias* (CPO) (Dutrillaux et al. 1982, Moulin et al. 2008). Chromosome numbers from reference karyotypes are displayed. Homologies with human chromosomes (HSA) are indicated. Ancestral chromosomes 20 and 21 are associated on this figure as their homologs are fused in all Cercopithecini species karyotyped to date.

Table S1: PCR primers used for phylogenetic studies

Gene (region)	Full name	PCR primers		T _a	Source
ABCA1 (intron)	ATP Binding Cassette Subfamily A Member 1	forward	CCTCCATCTTTTCAGCTCTACCTAC	57 °C	Perelman et al. (2011)
		reverse	ACAAGAGCCTGGAGATTGGATAAC		
BRCA2 (exon + intron)	Breast Cancer Type 2 Susceptibility	forward	CAGTTATTTATTACCCAGAGGCTGA	65 °C	This study
		reverse	CAACTACACTACTCTGTAAACGTGCAG		
CFTR (intron)	Cystic Fibrosis Transmembrane Conductance Regulator	forward	CTCTGTGAACACAGGATAGAAGC	67 °C	Perelman et al. (2011)
		reverse	TTACCTCCAGGAGGCTCAAAGCC		
DENND5A (exon + intron)	DENN Domain Containing 5A	forward	CCAGAGTTATCATGGCCAATC	67 °C	Perelman et al. (2011)
		reverse	GTACCAAGCAAGAAGCTGGG		
ERC2 (exon + intron)	ELKS/RAB6-interacting/CAST family member 2	forward	AGCTCATCCTCCTCCTGGTTTAG	67 °C	Perelman et al. (2011)
		reverse	CTCCTTGAGGATCTCCAGCAAC		
LRPPRC-169 (intron)	Leucine Rich Pentatricopeptide Repeat Containing 169	forward	CTTGGGATTGATGAGAATAATTTAG	65 °C	This study
		reverse	GCATTCTGACAGATGACAAAGTT		
TTR (intron)	Transthyretin	forward	CGGTGAGTGTTTCTGGGACA	65 °C	This study
		reverse	GCCCTGGGTGTAGGGAAGA		
ZFX (intron)	Zinc Finger Protein X-Linked	forward	GAGAATCTATGTCAGCATAAAGCAG	63 °C	This study
		reverse	GGAGTATGAGTGCTCAAACCAA		

Note: T_a corresponds to annealing temperature.

Table S2: GenBank sequences included in phylogenetic studies

	ABCA1	BRCA2	CFTR	DENND5A	ERC2
<i>Allenopithecus nigroviridis</i>	HM765265	HM763634	HM763500	HM759174	HM762247
<i>Allochrocebus lhoesti</i>	HM765294	HM763643	HM763533	HM759183	HM762225
<i>Allochrocebus preussi</i>	PX880141*	PX880150*	PX880162*	PX880171*	PX880180*
<i>Allochrocebus solatus</i>	PX880143*	PX880152*	PX880164*	PX880173*	PX880182*
<i>Chlorocebus aethiops</i>	HM765274	HM763647	HM763541	HM759189	HM762292
<i>Chlorocebus sabaesus</i>	HM765309	HM763649	HM763542	HM759190	HM762310
<i>Cercopithecus albogularis</i>	HM765273	HM763638	HM763528	HM759178	HM762227
<i>Cercopithecus ascanius</i>	HM765280	HM763639	HM763529	HM759179	HM762228
<i>Cercopithecus campbelli</i>	PX880137*	PX880144*	PX880155*	PX880165*	PX880174*
<i>Cercopithecus cephus</i>	PX880138*	PX880145*	PX880156*	PX880166*	PX880175*
<i>Cercopithecus diana</i>	HM765288	HM763641	HM763531	HM759181	HM762313
<i>Cercopithecus erythrotis</i>	-	PX880146*	PX880157*	PX880167*	PX880176*
<i>Cercopithecus hamlyni</i>	HM765293	HM763642	HM763532	HM759182	HM762233
<i>Cercopithecus mitis</i>	-	HM763644	PX880158*	PX880168*	PX880177*
<i>Cercopithecus mona</i>	HM765416	PX880147*	PX880159*	HM759185	HM762291
<i>Cercopithecus nictitans</i>	PX880139*	PX880148*	PX880160*	PX880169*	PX880178*
<i>Cercopithecus petaurista</i>	HM765306	HM763645	HM763535	HM759186	HM762217
<i>Cercopithecus pogonias</i>	PX880140*	PX880149*	PX880161*	PX880170*	PX880179*
<i>Cercopithecus roloway</i>	PX880142*	PX880151*	PX880163*	PX880172*	PX880181*
<i>Cercopithecus wolffi</i>	HM765311	HM763646	HM763536	HM759187	HM762257
<i>Erythrocebus patas</i>	HM765317	PX880153*	HM763547	HM759194	HM762311
<i>Miopithecus ogouensis</i>	HM765351	HM763670	-	HM759213	HM762215
<i>Macaca sylvanus</i>	HM765355	PX880154*	HM763582	HM759208	HM762214
<i>Cercocebus torquatus</i>	HM765310	HM763637	HM763527	HM759177	HM762220
<i>Mandrillus sphinx</i>	HM765354	HM763669	HM763586	HM759212	HM762252
<i>Colobus guereza</i>	HM765292	HM763651	HM763543	HM759192	HM762317

(Table S2, 1/2)

	LRPPRC-169	SRY	TTR	ZFX
<i>Allenopithecus nigroviridis</i>	HM761071	AF284331	HM757630	HM757022
<i>Allochrocebus lhoesti</i>	PX880188*	AY048067	HM757639	HM757030
<i>Allochrocebus preussi</i>	PX880192*	AY665642	PX880200*	PX880210*
<i>Allochrocebus solatus</i>	PX880194*	AY665643	PX880202*	PX880212*
<i>Chlorocebus aethiops</i>	HM761081	JF293182	HM757645	HM757034
<i>Chlorocebus sabaeus</i>	HM761082	KC843986	HM757647	HM757036
<i>Cercopithecus albogularis</i>	HM761075	EF517797	HM757634	HM757025
<i>Cercopithecus ascanius</i>	PX880183*	EF517798	HM757635	HM757026
<i>Cercopithecus campbelli</i>	PX880184*	AY665639	-	PX880203*
<i>Cercopithecus cephus</i>	PX880185*	AY450883	PX880195*	PX880204*
<i>Cercopithecus diana</i>	PX880186*	AY665633	HM757637	HM757028
<i>Cercopithecus erythrotis</i>	PX880187*	-	PX880196*	PX880205*
<i>Cercopithecus hamlyni</i>	HM761077	AY450884	HM757638	HM757029
<i>Cercopithecus mitis</i>	PX880189*	AY048069	PX880197*	PX880206*
<i>Cercopithecus mona</i>	-	AF284332	HM757641	PX880207*
<i>Cercopithecus nictitans</i>	PX880190*	AY450887	PX880198*	PX880208*
<i>Cercopithecus petaurista</i>	HM761080	AY897617	HM757643	HM757032
<i>Cercopithecus pogonias</i>	PX880191*	EF517799	PX880199*	PX880209*
<i>Cercopithecus roloway</i>	PX880193*	-	PX880201*	PX880211*
<i>Cercopithecus wolffi</i>	-	AY450889	HM757644	HM757033
<i>Erythrocebus patas</i>	HM761084	AY048073	HM757651	HM757040
<i>Miopithecus ogouensis</i>	HM761102	-	HM757669	HM757059
<i>Macaca sylvanus</i>	HM761098	AF284326	HM757664	HM757054
<i>Cercocebus torquatus</i>	HM761074	HM757968	HM757633	HM757024
<i>Mandrillus sphinx</i>	HM761101	AF284330	HM757668	HM757058
<i>Colobus guereza</i>	HM761083	JF293183	HM757649	HM757038

(Table S2, 2/2)

Note: GenBank accession numbers corresponding to newly generated sequences are marked with an asterisk (*). For these sequences, specimen identification numbers as well as additional metadata (e.g., collection date and origin) are provided within the 'source' features of the respective GenBank records.

Table S3: Specimens from the TCCV, RBCell collection (MNHN) included in cytogenomic studies

Species	MNHN-TCCV ID	Source
<i>Allenopithecus nigroviridis</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0020	Ménagerie du Jardin des Plantes, MNHN, Paris, France, 1979
<i>Allochrocebus lhoesti</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0292	Ménagerie du Jardin des Plantes, MNHN, Paris, France, 1998
<i>Allochrocebus solatus</i>	MNHN-TCCV-1073	International Center for Medical Research, Franceville, Gabon, 2012
<i>Cercopithecus ascanius</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0028	Ménagerie du Jardin des Plantes, MNHN, Paris, France, 1979
<i>Cercopithecus cephus</i>	MNHN-TCCV-1053	International Center for Medical Research, Franceville, Gabon, 2012
<i>Cercopithecus diana</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0003	Ménagerie du Jardin des Plantes, MNHN, Paris, France, 1978
<i>Cercopithecus erythrotis</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0135	Paimpont Biological Station, Rennes 1 University, France, 1984
<i>Cercopithecus mitis</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0180	Ménagerie du Jardin des Plantes, MNHN, Paris, France, 1986
<i>Cercopithecus mona</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0025	Ménagerie du Jardin des Plantes, MNHN, Paris, France, 1979
<i>Cercopithecus nictitans</i>	MNHN-TCCV-1089	International Center for Medical Research, Franceville, Gabon, 2013
<i>Cercopithecus pogonias</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0348	International Center for Medical Research, Franceville, Gabon, 2001
<i>Cercopithecus roloway</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0668	Ménagerie du Jardin des Plantes, MNHN, Paris, France, 2003
<i>Erythrocebus patas</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0006	Pasteur Institute, Lyon, France, 1978
<i>Macaca sylvanus</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0030	Ménagerie du Jardin des Plantes, MNHN, Paris, France, 1979
<i>Colobus angolensis</i>	MNHN-TCCV-0005	Basel Zoo, Switzerland, 1978

Note: The specimens that were recently collected in the International Center for Medical Research, Franceville, Gabon, were part of a program rescuing guenons that had been orphaned by hunting (MNHN-TCCV-1053, 1089, 0348) or living in a semi-free-ranging colony (MNHN-TCCV-1073) (Dilger et al., 2013; Motsch et al., 2015; Cacheux et al., 2025) (ethical permit n° FR1207510445-I).

Table S4: Oligo-FISH probe sequences and associated labels

Probe	Pattern (5'-3')	Label
C1a	TcCCtTtGcCaAtTcCAc	3'Cy3
C1b	AcTgCtCtGtGtTcTGtTa	3'Digoxygenin
C2a	TcACtTtGcAaAtTcCAc	5'AlexaFluor488
C2b	AcTgCtTtGtGtTcTGtTa	3'Cy5
C3a	CaGtTcTcAGaTtCcAcA	3'Digoxygenin
C3b	GcCcTaTaGtCtTcAaAg	3'Biotin
C4a	GtGaCtTcCAcTcAcTgA	3'Biotin
C4a'	TgAtGtGtGaCtTcCAcT	3'Digoxygenin
C4b	aGcTGtATtTcGTgGaGc	3'Biotin
C5a	TgAaTtCaGaGaAcAcAg	3'Biotin
C6a	CaTtTtCcTtCaAgAaTcC	3'Digoxygenin

Notes:

Design and patterns: The design methodology and target patterns were previously published in Cacheux et al. (2016, 2018). LNA (Locked Nucleic Acid) modifications are written in lower case, while classic nucleotides are written in upper case.

C1 family specificity (Cacheux et al. 2018): Probe C1a targets C1 sequences using a nucleotide pattern that is conserved in the C5 subfamily but is not conserved in the C6 subfamily. Probe C1b targets C1 sequences using a nucleotide pattern that is conserved in the C6 subfamily but is not conserved in the C5 subfamily.

C1/C2 Cross-Hybridization Control (Cacheux et al. 2016, 2018): Probes C1b and C2b target the same nucleotide site, differing only by a single nucleotide in their consensus sequence. Consequently, these two probes must be used together to prevent cross-hybridization (i.e., non-specific hybridization of probe C1b on C2 sequences and non-specific hybridization of probe C2b on C1 sequences).

Table S5: Summary of Oligo-FISH probe sets used per species

		C1a	C1b	C2a	C2b	C3a	C3b	C4a	C4a'	C4b	C5a	C5a 68 °C	C6a
AC	<i>C. mitis</i>	+		+			+		+		+	+	+
	<i>C. nictitans</i>	+		+			+		+		+	+	+
	<i>C. ascanius</i>	+		+			+		+		+	+	+
	<i>C. erythrotis</i>	+		+			+		+		+	+	+
	<i>C. cephus</i>	+		+	+		+		+		+	+	+
	<i>C. pogonias</i>	+	+	+	+		+	+	+		+	+	+
	<i>C. mona</i>	+		+			+		+		+	+	+
	<i>C. diana</i>	+		+			+		+		+	+	+
	<i>C. roloway</i>	+		+	+		+		+		+	+	+
TC	<i>A. lhoesti</i>	+		+			+		+		+	+	+
	<i>A. solatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	<i>E. patas</i>	+		+	+		+		+		+	+	+
SC	<i>Allen. nigroviridis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+
Out	<i>M. sylvanus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+	+	+
	<i>C. paliatus</i>	+		+			+		+	+	+	+	+

Notes:

Clade Designations: AC: Arboreal Clade; TC: Terrestrial Clade; SC: Swamp Clade; Out: Outgroup species.

Methodology: The '+' symbol indicates the probe was used for FISH analysis of the species. The column C5a 68 °C indicates that the C5a probe was used with a high-stringency post-hybridization wash (68 °C vs. standard 63 °C).

Source of Data: Data pertaining to *C. solatus* (C1-C4) and *C. pogonias* (C1, C2, C5 and C6) are sourced from previously published results (Cacheux et al., 2016, 2018).

Table S6: Observed counts of alpha satellite family associations in *Cercopithecus pogonias* dimeric sequences.

Left	Right					
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	-	-	-	-	-	-
C2	-	2130	-	0	-	-
C3	-	3	-	162	-	-
C4	-	-	-	-	-	-
C5	-	-	-	-	-	-
C6	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	0	2133	0	162	0	0

Notes: This table displays the number of dimeric sequences (total N=2295) based on the classification of their left and right monomers into the C1–C6 alpha satellite families. The dimeric sequences were retrieved from *C. pogonias* genomic DNA via XmnI enzymatic digestion, gel electrophoresis fractionation, and Ion Torrent NGS (as described in the Fig. S3 legend). The analysis only includes the subset of dimers that did not contain the XmnI restriction site between their constitutive left and right monomers. The "-" sign indicates non-relevant associations where the corresponding family (C1, C4, C5, C6 on the left; C1, C3, C5, C6 on the right) was absent from the dataset. Left and right monomer associations are non-random: significant over-representation was observed for C2-C2 (2130 dimers) and C3-C4 (162 dimers) (P-value < 10⁻³, Pearson's Chi-squared test).

Table S7: Average sequence identities in alpha satellite families identified in Cercopithecini (C1-C6)

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
<i>A. solatus</i>	95%	85%	86%	83%	-	-
<i>C. pogonias</i>	95%	85%	87%	85%	95%	98%

Note: The average sequence identities for *A. solatus* (C1–C4) and *C. pogonias* (C1, C2, C5, and C6) were retrieved from previous studies (Cacheux et al., 2016, 2018). The sequence distance analysis and calculation of average sequence identities for the C3 and C4 families in *C. pogonias* were performed as part of the current study, following the methods described in those previous works and using specific subsets of randomly selected sequences within each family.

References

- Cacheux, L., Gerbault-Seureau, M., Motsch, P., Bed'Hom, B., & Richard, F. A. (2025). Chromosomal Polymorphism in Cercopithecini: Cytogenomics Provides Evidence for Reticulate Evolution and Incomplete Reproductive Isolation. *International Journal of Primatology*, 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10764-025-00483-5>
- Cacheux, L., Ponger, L., Gerbault-Seureau, M., Loll, F., Gey, D., Richard, F. A., & Escudé, C. (2018). The targeted sequencing of alpha satellite DNA in *Cercopithecus pogonias* provides new insight into the diversity and dynamics of centromeric repeats in old world monkeys. *Genome Biology and Evolution*, 10(7), 1837-1851. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gbe/evy109>
- Cacheux, L., Ponger, L., Gerbault-Seureau, M., Richard, F. A., & Escudé, C. (2016). Diversity and distribution of alpha satellite DNA in the genome of an Old World monkey: *Cercopithecus solatus*. *BMC genomics*, 17(1), 916. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-016-3246-5>
- Dutrillaux, B., Couturier, J., & Chauvier, G. (1980). Chromosomal evolution of 19 species of sub-species of Cercopithecinae. *Annales de Génétique*, 23(3), 133-143.
- Dutrillaux, B., Couturier, J., Muleris, M., Lombard, M., & Chauvier, G. (1982). Chromosomal phylogeny of forty-two species or subspecies of cercopithecoids (Primates Catarrhini). *Annales de génétique*, 25(2), 96-109.
- Dutrillaux, B., Dutrillaux, A. M., Lombard, M., Gautier, J. P., Cooper, R., Moysan, F., & Lernoould, J. M. (1988). The Karyotype of *Cercopithecus solatus* Harrison 1988, a New Species Belonging to *Cercopithecus lhoesti*, and Its Phylogenetic-Relationships with Other Guenons. *Journal of Zoology*, 215(4), 611-617. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7998.1988.tb02398.x>
- Dutrillaux, B., Viegas-Pequignot, E., Couturier, J., & Chauvier, G. (1978). Identity of euchromatic bands from man to Cercopithecidae: *Cercopithecus aethiops*, *Cercopithecus sabaesus*, *Erythrocebus patas*, and *Miopithecus talapoin*. *Human Genetics*, 45(3), 283-296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00278726>
- Dilger, C., Le Flohic, G., Campagne, N., & Motsch, P. (2013). Projet KIKI : Projet de conservation et de réintroduction des cercopithèques du Gabon. *Revue de primatologie*, (5). <https://doi.org/10.4000/primatologie.1479>
- Edgar, R. C. (2004). MUSCLE: a multiple sequence alignment method with reduced time and space complexity. *BMC bioinformatics*, 5(1), 113. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-5-113>

Motsch, P., Le Flohic, G., Dilger, C., Delahaye, A., Chateau-Smith, C., & Couette, S. (2015). Degree of terrestrial activity of the elusive sun-tailed monkey (*Cercopithecus solatus*) in Gabon: Comparative study of behavior and postcranial morphometric data. *American Journal of Primatology*, 77(10), 1060-1074. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajp.22441>

Moulin, S., Gerbault-Seureau, M., Dutrillaux, B., & Richard, F.A. (2008). Phylogenomics of African guenons. *Chromosome Research*, 16, 783-799. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10577-008-1226-6>

Perelman, P., Johnson, W. E., Roos, C., Seuánez, H. N., Horvath, J. E., Moreira, M. A., ... & Pecon-Slatery, J. (2011). A molecular phylogeny of living primates. *PLoS genetics*, 7(3), e1001342. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1001342>